

Studies in the Naphthathiazole Series. Part II.
The Methylation of 1-Anilino- α -naphthathiazole
and of 1-*p*-Bromoanilino- α -naphthathiazole.
The Aromatic Character of the Hetero-
cyclic Nucleus in α -Naphthathiazoles.

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It has been shown that on methylation, 1-amino- α -naphthathiazole (I $\leftrightarrow$ II) reacts exclusively in the amino phase yielding 1-imino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydro- α -naphthathiazole (III), unaccompanied by any detectable quantity of the isomeric methylamino- α -naphthathiazole (IV) (Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 941).

In the benzthiazole series, the reactivity of the semicyclic amidine system is also almost entirely in favour of the aminothiazole phase (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1385; Hunter and Styles, *ibid.*, 1928, 3019; Hunter and Pride, *ibid.*, 1929, 943). The introduction of a conjugated substituent such as the phenyl nucleus of the anilino grouping in 1-anilinobenzthiazole, however, enables the extra nuclear nitrogen atom of the triad system to compete with the heterocyclic nucleus for the double bond, with the production on methylation, of a mixture of isomeric methyl derivatives derived from both phases of the tautomeric system. This effect is

further enhanced by the presence of a *p*-bromosubstituent in the anilino grouping, since 1-*p*-bromoanilinobenzthiazole methylates apparently exclusively in the iminodihydrothiazole phase, yielding 4'-bromo-1-phenylmethylaminobenzthiazole (Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2190).

It was, therefore, of interest to examine the effect of replacement of a hydrogen atom of the amino group in 1-amino- α -naphthathiazole by a phenyl radical on the reactivity of the semicyclic amidine towards alkylating agents, and the methylation of 1-anilino- α -naphthathiazole (V $\leftrightarrow$ VI) was investigated. On methylation by means of methyl iodide under conditions similar to those used in the case of 1-amino- α -naphthathiazole, however, this base reacted completely in the amino phase (V) yielding 1-phenylimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydro- α -naphthathiazole (VII); no trace of the isomeric methylaminonaphthathiazole (VIII), which has been synthesised from 1-chloro- α -naphthathiazole and methylaniline, being capable of detection.

Since the attraction of the phenyl nucleus for the $\alpha\beta$ -double bond in 1-anilino- α -naphthathiazole is evidently insufficient to overcome the effect of internal aromatic conjugation of the heterocyclic ring, the investigation was extended to the 1-*p*-bromoanilino derivative (IX $\leftrightarrow$ X).

1-*p*-Bromoanilino- α -naphthathiazole, however, behaved similarly to 1-anilino- α -naphthathiazole and methylated exclusively in the amino aromatic form (IX), yielding 1-*p*-bromophenylimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydro- α -naphthathiazole unaccompanied by any detectable quantity of 1-*p*-bromophenylmethylamino- α -naphthathiazole.

It is, therefore, evident that neither the anilino substituent in 1-anilino- α -naphthathiazole nor the *p*-bromoanilino substituent in 1-*p*-bromoanilino- α -naphthathiazole, possess sufficient attraction for the double bond of the semicyclic triad system to overcome the effect of internal aromatic conjugation in the thiazole nucleus of the α -naphthathiazole complex.

A similar condition obtains in the 2-aminothiazoles themselves, since both 2-anilino-4-methylthiazole (Young and Crookes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 59) and 2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole (Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 147) react exclusively in the aminothiazole phase on treatment with methylating agents. It has furthermore been found that 2-*p*-bromoanilino-4-methylthiazole behaves similarly and yields 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3:4-dimethyl-2:3-dihydrothiazole in exclusion to other products, on methylation under the usual conditions (Hunter and Parken, unpublished experiments).

The behaviour of the 1-amino- α -naphthathiazoles, therefore, resembles that of the simple aminothiazoles much more closely than that of the 1-aminobenzthiazoles, and the heterocyclic nucleus in α -naphthathiazole is evidently more aromatic than in benzthiazole. The suggestion has been offered that a certain degree of aromatic character of the thiazole nucleus is lost when it is combined with a benzene ring as in benzthiazole due to the mutual effect of the aromatic nuclei, such as is witnessed in the naphthalene molecule (Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *loc. cit.*). If this is the case, it is clear that the disturbing effect of the benzene ring in benzthiazole is largely compensated by the presence of a second fused aromatic nucleus as in α -naphthathiazole. This question cannot, however, be discussed until the behaviour of other combinations of the thiazole ring with the naphthalene system have been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-Chloro- α -naphthathiazole was prepared by heating a mixture of β -naphthylthiocarbimide (4.6 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride

(5.2 g.) in sealed tube at 160—170° for 6 hours. The product was treated with water to decompose phosphorus halides and the mixture was extracted with chloroform and the chloroform was removed from the extract on a water-bath. The product obtained in this way had m.p. 79° and was pure enough for ordinary purposes (cf. Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 942)

1-Anilino- α -naphthathiazole was prepared by the condensation of 1-chloro- α -naphthathiazole and aniline, and separated from methyl alcohol-ethyl acetate in silky needles, m.p. 211-12°

The methylation of 1-anilino- α -naphthathiazole, the isolation of 1-phenylimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydro- α -naphthathiazole and the synthesis of 1-phenylmethylamino- α -naphthathiazole.—(i) A mixture of 1-anilino- α -naphthathiazole (1 g.) and methyl iodide (2 c.c.) was heated in a sealed tube at 100° for 12 to 13 hours. The product was treated with warm 20% potassium hydroxide and the mixture was kept for 1 hour and thereafter extracted with chloroform. The base obtained by removal of the chloroform from a steam-bath was fractionally crystallised from alcohol, when 1-phenylimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydro- α -naphthathiazole was obtained in glistening needles, m.p. 182°. (Found: S, 11.0. $C_{18}H_{14}N_2S$ requires S, 11.0 per cent). This methylation product appeared to be quite homogeneous and all attempts to isolate any traces of the isomeric 1-phenylmethylamino isomer proved unsuccessful. The picrate was prepared by mixing benzene solutions of the base (0.3 g.) and picric acid (0.25 g.) and warming the mixture on a steam-bath for a few minutes; it separated from benzene in glistening golden yellow plates, m.p. 218°. (Found: S, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{14}N_2S, C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires S, 6.1 per cent).

(ii) A mixture of 1-chloro- α -naphthathiazole (0.6 g.) and methylaniline (0.3 g.) was heated in a boiling tube over a small naked flame until a violent reaction took place. The cold condensation product was treated with aqueous ammonia and the mixture was boiled, when a resinous product was obtained which became semi-solid on cooling in a freezing mixture. This was dissolved in methyl alcohol and the solution was concentrated in a vacuum at laboratory temperature when the base was obtained as an oil which was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated by ammonia. Attempts to crystallise this product from methyl alcohol proved unsuccessful and it was, therefore, converted into the picrate by treatment with picric acid in benzene solution as in the

case of the phenyliminomethyl-dihydro isomer. The *picrate* of 1-phenylmethylamino- α -naphthathiazole separated from benzene in greenish yellow plates, m.p. 184°. (Found: S, 6.2. $C_{18}H_{14}N_2S$, $C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires S, 6.1 per cent). A mixture of this with the *picrate* of 1-phenylimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydro- α -naphthathiazole melted at 170-74°. A search of the mother liquors for traces of this *picrate* in an experiment, in which the whole of the methylation product of 1-anilino-naphthathiazole was dissolved in benzene and converted into *picrate*, proved fruitless.

Methylation of 1-p-bromoanilino- α -naphthathiazole, the isolation of 1-p-bromophenylimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydro- α -naphthathiazole and the synthesis of 1-p-bromophenylmethylamino- α -naphthathiazole.—1-p-Bromoanilino- α -naphthathiazole was prepared by condensation of equimolecular proportions of 1-chloro- α -naphthathiazole and *p*-bromoaniline, and had m.p. 256° after recrystallisation from alcohol—ethyl acetate (Hunter and Jones recorded m.p. 250°).

(i) A mixture of 1-p-bromoanilino- α -naphthathiazole (0.6 g.) and methyl iodide (1 c.c.) was heated in a sealed tube at 100° for 15 hours, and the product was basified with boiling 20% sodium hydroxide and extracted with chloroform. After removal of the chloroform and recrystallisation from alcohol, 1-p-bromophenylimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydro- α -naphthathiazole was obtained in glistening plates, m.p. 182°. (Found: Br, 22.4. $C_{17}H_{13}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 22.2 per cent). A careful search of the mother liquors failed to reveal any trace of the isomeric 1-p-bromophenylmethylamino isomer.

(ii) *p*-Bromomethylaniline was prepared with some difficulty by the following method. Acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) was added to methylaniline (20 g.) and the mixture was thereafter heated on a sand-bath under reflux for 25 hours. On concentration, methylacetanilide solidified and had m.p. 102° after being dried on porous earthenware. A solution of this acetyl derivative (27.8 g.) in glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) was treated with bromine (5 c.c. in 5 c.c. of the same solvent) in sunlight, when shining plates separated in the mixture during the course of 2-3 hours. The mixture was kept at laboratory temperature for a further 5 hours, diluted with water (4 vols.) and kept overnight when an oil separated which was extracted with ether. The viscous product obtained after removal of the ether was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid and the mixture was heated on a sand-bath

under reflux for 5 hours, cooled and basified when *p*-bromomethylaniline separated as an oil which was extracted with ether. A mixture of 1-chloro- α -naphthathiazole (0.5 g.) and *p*-bromomethylaniline (0.6 g.) was gently heated over a small flame until a violent reaction took place and the cooled product was basified with ammonia. The *p*-bromophenylmethylamino base was extracted with ether and the product obtained by removal of the ether was recrystallised with some difficulty from alcohol, when it formed small crystals, m.p 245°. (Found: Br, 22.3. C₁₇H₁₃N₂BrS requires Br, 22.4 per cent).

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